

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING WRITING (THE USE OF “CHARACTER WHEEL” METHOD)

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ABSTRACT

This article studies the problems of teaching writing and develops learners' writing habits and skills. It gives information about effective methods of teaching writing.

The developing of the language skills has always been a very hard and an interesting task. An English teacher always faces a challenge to teach the writing skill to the foreign language students especially at university. As one of the language skills, writing is excelled only when the other three language skills are excelled. It is the combination of process and product. It involves mastery in grammar and vocabulary to present the message. It requires self-knowledge to express the thought process. It is felt a dry exercise, only used to write the exams. Though the students have the knowledge in English finds it difficult to express. Most of them depend on rote system to get through the examination. If the teacher is asked to teach the students whose English knowledge is absolutely poor at university, it becomes a challenge. We tried all the traditional methods and modern methods to teach writing here in our university and found out the reasons for the problem.

The process of writing suggests that we can actually teach students how to write with

coherence, an appropriate grammar structure and an acceptable spelling. Being a teacher it is important to discuss the objectives of writing skill and let the students know that their script will speak in their absence. The main reason for teaching writing is to help the students express their thoughts into words. One of the effective ways to do this is to motivate the students and make them aware of the steps involved in effective writing. Four reasons why students dislike writing are:

1. It leaves as more permanent record of proficiency than speaking; so it seems a threat for them.
2. Students feel that they lack sufficient knowledge of the language.
3. Students believe that writing must be grammatically correct.
4. They think that formal correctness must be achieved at their very first attempt.

In terms of teaching writing for language learners teacher should consider some aspects in teaching writing. Every single lesson requires careful preparation- need to think about a variety of techniques, activities

and teaching aids to make the lesson appealing to the students. In many classes, attention in writing is very limited because writing is only to be as a testing tool. It may be that makes teaching and learning writing skill to be bored. By the time the students join the university, they are expected to have some knowledge in grammar, spelling of the words, word order and vocabulary. Though they hail from vernacular medium, they are exposed to English language teaching at certain level of their schooling. Though English has been introduced as a language study, they learn it as a subject. Hence, they do not show any interest to use it as a language; instead they feel that it is a subject to be passed.

Secondly, most of the time the students show interest to copy, memorize and present in the examinations. Unfortunately, the examination exams the retention power of the students and give less importance to the language aspect. Hence they are not aware of the various types of writing and the suitable language to use accordingly.

Thirdly, the students face lots of problems at university, when they fail to discriminate the styles of writing and methods and vocabulary to use under different headings.

Fourthly, the causes of not showing interest in writing may be lack of motivation to learn English and the teacher's lack of interest. Environmental reasons include the use of the mother tongue, few opportunities to practice English, and isolated culture.

Finally, the writing activities should be geared to their needs and interests. They should be linked to the real life whenever possible. When we talk about writing is necessary to remember that there are three inseparable aspects when teaching it; Writing as a channel of a Foreign Language is the use of it alongside listening, speaking and reading

in the process of learning important elements of the language;

In the present work we pretend to give useful information about the developing of writing skills and give some practical teaching ideas for this purpose contributing to improve teacher's knowledge about this topic.

Then, we would like to state what the word practical means. From our point of view, a practical teaching idea has something to do with a good idea, characterized by being attractive, exciting, and applicable to real life and taking into account the environment, context and most of all, the learners' needs and interests. Thus, teachers should know how to teach writing to be effective. Now we are going to present some effective methods, which motivate students, to teach writing skills.

The name of the method is called **“Character wheel”** which is more effective method. In order to use this method in class, teacher should collect a picture from each student and divide the class in two groups. Then the teacher distributes a picture to each student. Now each student names their pictures and writes on the paper under the picture. Then the student passes the picture to the person on his or her right and this person adds the age, occupation and again passes next student who continues completing. They may also write marital status and size of the family, address, hobbies and interests, one thing the person loves and one thing the person hates. The next it will be imagination step. Each student writes two sentences under the picture about “What did they do yesterday”? Then the student passes the picture to the person on his or her left. After having ended the paper, it should be returned to the person who made the first contribution. Let the students read and find their errors. This method not only improves student's writing skills but also develops their critical and creative thinking skills.

It took some of our time to motivate the students. Later on the small group activities really developed a competitive spirit among the students. We prepared the learning objectives for our lessons and understood our students' learning styles and started implementing successfully and encouraged to

students to practice writing as a skill. We used instructional scaffolding in learning process to promote deeper level of learning. The support, that has been given, tailored to the needs of the students with a goal to help the students achieving his or her learning goals.

References:

1. Hutchinson, T., and A. Waters. 1987. *English for Specific Purposes*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. Print
 2. Linse, C & Nunan, D. 2005. *Practical English Language Teaching: Young Learners*. New York: McGraw-Hill Companies. Print
 3. Zerín, S. 2007. *Teaching Writing to young Learners*. BRAC University
- Richard, J. and Rodgers, T., (2001). *Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching*. Second Edition. Cambridge University Press. Print